

Learning street representation by aligning visual features from street-view and satellite imagery

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Abstract:

Streets are the fundamental structural units of urban systems, closely tied to human mobility, transportation, and spatial semantics. Effectively representing streets offers deep insights into the intricate complexities of street geographic information. Recent advances have been driven by the integration of multi-modal geospatial data, which allows for a more comprehensive and expressive understanding of street geographic phenomena. However, a key challenge remains in ensuring the consistent expression of multi-modal geographic information within unified street representations, due to the heterogeneity and misalignment across different data modalities.

In view of this, we propose a novel street representation learning model that leverages the intrinsic complementarity between satellite imagery (SI) and street view imagery (SVI). Specifically, we utilize two dedicated pretrained vision large language models to obtain the initial embeddings of SIs and SVIs. These view-specific visual embeddings are then processed through a graph transformer network, which serves as the encoder to capture the spatial proximity among streets. To align the visual information from the two views of streets, we introduce a multi-view visual feature alignment objective based on the contrastive learning paradigm. The multi-view visual feature alignment objective trains the model in a self-supervised manner by maximizing the consistency between SI- and SVI-derived features in the learned representation space, thereby encouraging the model to capture shared semantic structures across the two views of streets.

Extensive experiments on real-world urban datasets demonstrate that the proposed model significantly outperforms baseline approaches across geographic tasks, i.e., traffic speed prediction and traffic volume prediction. And, together with ablation study and parameter study all demonstrate the superiority of the proposed model. This study provides a new perspective in street representation from the multi-view visual feature alignment of SI and SVI.